

The perception of government in remote ethnic communities of East Siberia

Fartyshev Arseniy Nikolaevich¹ and Razmakhnina Julia Sergeevna²

Abstract:

The issues of electoral behavior and the interaction of the electorate and power among the indigenous small people of the soyots, who live in one of the most remote regions of Russia - the Okinsky rayon of Buryatia, are covered. Soyots as a typical long remote community in Russia are characterized by a higher level of support for pro-government candidates and the ruling party, which is based on a sense of non-participation in the federal agenda due to their geographical remoteness, which implies their conformist behavior. In the Okinsky district, there is a high activity of local authorities and a variety of non-trivial political practices, which are described in the article. A pronounced ethnic feature is the high level of political influence among religious actors (buddhist lamas and shamans), that is low researched yet, as well as the presence of public institutions that defend the issues of legislative initiatives at the federal level, which in perception are equated with government. The main problems of soyots that have importance for political campaigns was revealed. We have identified the less perception distance between municipality governments in local long remote communities according to the same distance in urban communities.

Keywords:

electoral geography, geography of power, electoral motivation, Russia, political system, remote areas, ethnic peripheries, Okinskiy district.

¹ Candidate of Sciences (Geography), Head of Laboratory of Geo-Resource Studies and Political Geography, V. B. Sochava Institute of Geography SB RAS, Associate Professor of Department of Political Science, History and Regional Studies Irkutsk State University.

² Candidate of Sciences (Geography), Researcher, Laboratory of Geo-Resource Studies and Political Geography, V. B. Sochava Institute of Geography SB RAS.

Introduction

The ethnic peripheries of both Russia and the whole world are of particular interest in electoral geography, because, as a rule, there are anomalous voting results there in relation to the average level. In relation to concept of failed state, governmental power cannot cover all of the territory of the state and control the space homogeneously (Jessop, 2016), at the first time an intension decreased in remote peripheries at it's rightfully for large countries. Relatively large ethnic minorities can both create their own parties, and among them, other types of “socio-electoral cleavages” can significantly influence (Lipset, Rokkan, 1967). In conditions where there is no party that represents the interests of ethnic minorities in the elections, the votes of local ethnic communities can be extremely unpredictable: both sharply opposed, and, on the contrary, increased vote for the dominating party. Small ethnic communities are more homogeneous, but the main issue lies in formation of the electoral cultures of such communities.

The purpose of all the work was to assess the role of the ethnic factor in political-geographical processes and socio-demographic and economic development of Eastern Siberia.

Methods and data

The Okinsky district of Buryatia is an area inhabited predominantly by a non-Russian population (about 94%) and is part of the ethnic periphery. Soyots are included in list of indigenous ethnoses of Siberia (Bezrukov and Razmakhina. 2021.). According to official data the share of soyots in Okinsky district is 60 %. In conditions of its hard-accessibility and expressed peripheral location, Okinsky district represents a well researching polygon for political and social-geographical science.

Map: Administrative map of Okinsky district of Buryatia

The statistical analysis based on official data of federal election campaigns for the period 2000-2023 of presidential and duma's elections (excluding of single-member constituency elections) that was extracted from governmental automatized system "Vybory".

The qualitative analysis based on field researches that has been waged by authors in Okinsky distict of Peruplic Buryatiya in June of 2021 and 2022. A survey research with elements of semistructured interview (n=279) that took 19,5% of population that have active electoral right of settlements (uluses Sorok, Khurba, Bokson, Nyurgan, Khuzhir, Sayany, Shasnur, Obtoy, Tusmak). Furthermore it was collected the individual in-depth interviews with a representatives of local ethnic and political elite – the heads of municipalities, directors of schools, religious and public firures.

Results

Decision to vote of soyots

In the Okinsky district during the 2000–2010s there is an abnormally increased turnout in the elections, as well as the percentage of votes for the pro-governmental party and candidates representing this party. This situation is not unique in Russia, and is typical for many ethnically non-Russian territories (Ignatov et al, 2022; Shkel et al, 2022). The average excess of turnout in the Okinsky district in relation to the all-Russian level is 14%, and in relation to the regional average it is even higher – 15.9%. It shown on table 1.

Table 1: The average variation of results of federal elections in Buryatia during 2000-2021

Raion Buryatia	of Share russian / non russian ethics	turnout	Average variation by districts from total level			
			Edinaya Rossiya ("dominating party")	Communist Party	Liberal- democratic party	Against all
Barguzin	75,5/22,7	-0,27	1,16	1,30	-1,14	0,12
Baunt	77,6/19,4	1,75	0,95	-0,85	0,61	-0,16
Bichura	87,1/12,1	-4,25	-6,56	8,06	0,57	-0,24
Severobaikalsk	84,2/4,4	-5,87	-9,40	4,36	3,30	0,05

Ulan-Ude	63,6/32,8	<i>-4,35</i>	<i>-10,17</i>	6,31	-1,11	0,05
Dzhida	55,6/41,3	2,41	2,51	1,50	-2,94	0,28
Evarninskiy	43,6/55,1	13,93	6,03	0,08	-3,52	0,27
Zaigraevo	83,1/13,5	-4,51	-1,75	2,79	0,16	-0,08
Zakamenskiy	32,4/65,8	13,43	14,30	<i>-3,32</i>	<i>-5,34</i>	-0,33
Ivolginskiy	37,5/60,8	-2,26	-4,03	4,03	-2,87	-0,05
Kabanskiy	92,4/5,2	-4,55	<i>-7,16</i>	3,08	2,84	0,22
Kizhinga	36,3/62,2	14,43	9,72	<i>-2,82</i>	<i>-5,29</i>	0,48
Kurumkan	30,1/68,6	8,52	6,51	<i>-1,67</i>	<i>-5,04</i>	-0,18
Kyakhta	72,7/23,4	2,85	3,41	-0,39	-0,02	0,05
Muyskiy	84,3/6,1	<i>-12,38</i>	<i>-4,65</i>	0,30	4,18	-0,18
Mukhorshibir	79,9/17,8	-0,39	0,06	2,41	-0,47	-0,16
Okinskiy	6,2/93,4	14,94	5,21	0,38	<i>-5,47</i>	0,23
Pribaikalskiy	95,8/2,3	-1,13	-3,65	1,32	2,01	0,01
Severobaikalskiy	85,5/8,0	0,42	-2,20	1,58	4,09	-0,21
Selenginskiy	61,7/34,4	-1,00	0,85	0,38	-0,89	-0,17
Tarbagatay	92,2/6,1	1,71	-1,30	3,29	-0,31	-0,06
Tunka	33,8/65,2	8,47	4,74	1,60	<i>-4,66</i>	0,07
Khorinskiy	62,1/35,1	7,86	6,65	<i>-1,63</i>	-2,90	-0,01

(maximum values are marked in dark, minimum values are marked in italics)

Statistical analysis reveals that the districts with high share of indigenous people have the heightened rate of turnout and result of pro-governance party in federal elections campaigns of 2000-2021. In opposite most of them has decreased rate of

Communist party and Liberal-Democratic party. Why it has been happening? Can we expect this effect in future?

Based on the results of field research, a really high motivation to vote was revealed, which determines a high level of turnout and a low level of absenteeism. According to the theory of electoral motivation by A. Blais and J.-F. Daoust (2020), the decision to vote or abstain depends on the answers to four key questions: Do I like the policy? Am I required to vote? Do I care about the result? Is it easy to vote? Using the example of the Soyots, the main factor is the duty to vote (“it’s my duty”, “because it’s necessary”), at the same time, the interest in politics and the interest in the voting results is extremely low. Respondents also note that they are afraid not to vote because they want to appear antisocial to others (“what will others think of me if I don’t vote, that I’m somehow different?”). Thus, among the Soyots, the ethical and social aspect of voting motivation predominates, which, on the one hand, is typical for compact communities (Ali, Lin, 2013), on the other hand, is a local feature of the electoral culture at the all-Russian level, where other factors of voting motivation are mixed in.

Elections of parties of soyots

Soyots are characterized by a higher level of support for pro-government candidates and the ruling party, which is based on a sense of non-participation in the federal agenda due to their geographical remoteness, which implies their conformist behavior. In the Okinsky district, there is a high activity of local authorities and a variety of non-trivial political practices (in detail: (Fartyshev et al, 2023)). In conditions of political isolation and local budget deficits, local authorities become more important than even the regional government.

Statistical analysis shows that areas with a high share of the indigenous population (Eravninsky, Zakamensky, Kizhinginsky, Kurumkansky, Okinsky, Tunkinsky districts) on average in the federal election campaigns of 2003-2021 have higher turnout rates, voted more actively for pro-government candidates, while most of them have one of the lowest indicators for the Communist Party of the Russian Federation and the Liberal Democratic Party. At the same time, it should be noted that there is a high dispersion of values for the indicators of the Communist Party of the Russian Federation, but some of the lowest dispersion values for turnout and votes for power. Thus, in the 2011 elections to the State Duma of the Russian Federation in the Okinsky district, the Communist Party (CPRF) received the highest value in Eastern Siberia - 32%, while in the presidential elections in 2004 and 2018 the anomalous result of the Okinsky district was voting for the pro-government candidate V.V. Putin (84.2% and 83.1%, respectively).

Table 2: Preferences of the Soyots to main political parties in Russia (n=270).

Party	Positive	Neutral	Negative
Edinaya Rossiya (for existing power)	163	84	23
Communitic party	78	164	28
Liberal-democratic party	54	156	60
Spravedlivaya Rossia (social-democratic party)	46	189	35

The survey data confirms a high level of positive attitude towards “Edinaya Rossiya”, but it is still less than what electoral statistics show. The negative perception of the Liberal-democratic party comes mainly from the historical sentence about the nationalist character of this party, which has been entrenched since the 1990s, although in fact such slogans have ceased to be used by 2020. The attitude towards the Communist Party is mostly neutral. On the one hand, an olders remember the forced extermination of Soyot language speakers during the years of the Red Terror; on the other hand, the modern image of the party is poorly linked to the events of the distant past. During the Soviet period, there was no significant industrialization of the territory of the Okinskiy district, with the exception of a few kolkhozes. Neutrality towards the social-democratic party Spravedlivaya Rossia is expressed rather by poor awareness of it, its political agenda and political leaders. The specific of all-russian political culture is memorability of party based on authorities and personality of leaders.

The key characteristic of the electoral behavior of ethnic peripheral territories is conformism, understood as an individual’s uncritical perception of the existing order of things and refusal to develop his own position, which is expressed in voting for the current government again and again (Wantchekon, 2003). As a result of our research, it was revealed that the conformity of the Soyots lies not so much in a passive political position, but in various forms of clientelism (Fartyshhev et al, 2023). In exchange for solving local problems of remote rural settlements, loyalty to one or another party is a subject of bargaining, since in conditions of compact living of small ethnic groups, the mobilization of electoral resources is facilitated, which creates conditions for the use of the administrative factor (Veselova and Tcherenev, 2018).

Alternative political leaders in Okinskiy district

Historically, the main interaction in the Oka region is between representatives of shamanism and buddhism. In many ways, shamans and lamas are the bearers of power and high authority among the population. The main problems that the local population prefers to solve not through government agencies, but through religious leaders are the treatment of diseases, the search for a missing livestock, problems in family. It is typical that the relationship between religious leaders is complementary: the lama, if it is impossible to help or the forecast does not come true, refers people to the shaman and vice versa. Moreover, several shamans can act in one village, but only one lama, as a spiritual mentor, has significant political weight. This phenomenon explains the tendency of institutionalization of clergy as political actors. In modern Buryatia, shamans are organized into legally formalized professional communities or carry out their activities individually (Mikhalev, 2022). With their authority, they help solve many social and political problems, often succeeding where the official government or police is powerless.

In addition, there are elements of civil society in the area that are positively perceived by the population and through which it is possible to achieve certain political decisions. Issues of legislative initiatives regarding the rights of Soyots are resolved not through official representatives of the electorate in legislatures, but through a public organization - the Association of Indigenous Peoples of Siberia and the Far North. Its recognition among the Soyot population turned out to be high: among the initiatives it implemented, respondents were able to name the reduction of the threshold for entering the retirement age for representatives of indigenous peoples by five years, the revival of the practice of teaching the Soyot language in primary school, obtaining preferential budget places in higher educational institutions of the region (not yet implemented in practice), etc. In the perception of the population, the association is practically equated with power structures, since the main office of the Soyot representative office is located directly in the district administration building.

Rating of political problems

In the next step we asked a respondents about the main problems that should be represented at in election program of candidates. Which one is specify for ethnic community of indigenous people and which one is regular in the context of all-Russian political discourse. What worries the Soyot population most. In the next we show it into the list:

1) Road Mondy-Orlik – 36,8 % from those who answered. Okinsky district connected with other part of Buryatia by unpaved road about 150 km length, that it had been constructed only in 1993. Before that the relation with district had been worked as horse-drawn and aircraft transport (Kuklina et al., 2022). The supply and product prices in district are depended from condition of this road, moreover it can be closed at the rainy period, and that's why it so bother for natives At the time

fencing from the outer world in case of automobile roads might be a own chase of indigenous people (Schweitzer, 2017). In nomad cultures the issue of transport accessibility is being comprehended different than in sedentary ones (Konstantinov, 2009). But the gradual departure of the Soyots from a nomadic lifestyle to a semi-nomadic and sedentary one forces them to take more and more attention to infrastructural benefits.

2) Development of agriculture and especially livestock farming (20,6 %). That shows the main economic interest that is in need of fiscal facilities. So, such governmental initiatives in agriculture as far-eastern hectar (agreement for free use of land) do not so efficient as it purposed at the first time of realization of this program (Zhuravskaya and Ryzhova, 2021), due to intension of natives to use it for privatization of moving and pasturelands.

3) Electricity of homesteads (8,8 %). There is only one branch of electricity power line (110 kW) to neighboring Tunkinskiy district and from time to time power surges and failures are happened in time of climate cataclysm. This problem is of an infrastructural nature, inherent for most of remote peripheral territories, and therefore cannot be attributed to the exceptional cases of Soyots.

4) Quotas for applicants (8,8 %). Several regions of Russia have a practice to give additional budget places for indigenous representatives to studying in university, such as in Sakha(Yakutiya) region where this advantage was realized for 71 native person, that was conquest by mentioned Association of Indigenous Peoples of Siberia and the Far North. But incase of Buryatia it's not working.

5) Problem of learning and speaking in mother language (8,8 %). The Soyot language is considered extinct, since there is not a single native speaker left, but all of the soyots are well speak in Buryat. According to informants, in 1926–1927. purges of those who knew the language took place in the area: “Other peoples of the Eastern Sayan of Turkic origin - Tuvans-Todzhins, Tofalars - retained their language, but Soyot language was banned by Soviet Russia”. Nowadays optional teaching of the Soyot language is conducted only in school grades 1-4 and it is not used in everyday life. On the one hand, the Soyots express concern about the extinction of their original language, but on the other hand, at the present stage, replacement by the Buryat language has already occurred naturally.

6) Problems in licensing hunting and fishing (2,9 %). Indigenous people have a right for free using natural resources on the *Коренные малочисленные народы вправе бесплатно пользоваться природными ресурсами в границах territories of traditional nature management*, but nevertheless they have to get a license. According to the informant: “It's difficult to receive it. At this time there is no hunting inspector in our area. The hunting county is united with the Mukhorshibirsky district, so the hunting inspector practically does not visit the Okinsky district. On the one hand, the legislative norm does not work, but there is also no supervision over violation of environmental rules for Soyots.

7) The problem of catching wolves (1%). The Soyots are predominantly pastoral people, and they take their herds to the mountains in the summer, where there is an acute problem of wolf overpopulation. There is a law norm about independently catching wolves, whereas the Federal Service for Supervision of Natural Resources buys wolf skins from the hunters. According to the informant: “We give 16 thousand rubles for a wolf. and we’ll hand it over, but there’s no inspector: we’ll have to go to Ulan-Ude.” However, in 2020, 168 were caught, which, although a large number, is not enough to protect the herds. As a result, many households remain in villages and do not go to the mountains because of fear of the wolf threat.

So, most of the problems have a social-economic aspect but they are characterized by local specific. There are many problems of ethnocultural nature like a reconstruction of language heritage and teaching of natural traditions that’s peculiarly for Okinskiy district and it is not conducted in electoral programs of political parties.

Conclusion

The uniqueness of the perception of political power among the soyots lies in the following features:

1. the motivation to vote is based on social and ethical aspects such as a fear of antisocial person appearing in compact community and a sense of duty to vote
2. we indicate a high level of support for pro-government candidates and the party in power is lied in conformist behavior and various forms of clientelism.
3. there are high activity of local authorities and non-trivial methods of solving local problems due to the shorter distance between the authorities and voters.
4. there is a high level of political influence among religious actors: buddhist lamas and shamans.
5. we observes the activity of public institutions in conditions of rural undeveloped political culture that defend issues of legislative initiatives at the federal level, which are equated to power.

The researching group will continue the researches: a surveing, interviews, included observation in different remote areas of Eastern Russia and we would like to invite to dialog to make interregional comparative studies of perception of government in remote areas.

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